

gave 10.3–13.4 t of fodder ha⁻¹ and their ratoon regrowth contributed 4.7–7.5 t of green manure biomass ha⁻¹. Incorporation of red gram stalks and ratooned green manure biomass contributed 16–55 kg N ha⁻¹ (Table 1).

Rice yield, obtained by incorporating sole *S. rostrata*/*S. aculeata* along with the application of 50 kg N ha⁻¹, was on a par with yield from the treatment with 100 kg N ha⁻¹, resulting in a savings of 50 kg N ha⁻¹. It was also found that after applying sole *Sesbania* spp. without fertilizer N, rice yields (3.6 t ha⁻¹) were on a par with yields obtained with 50 kg N ha⁻¹ alone (3.8 t ha⁻¹). These results show the possibility of saving 50 kg N ha⁻¹ by incorporating green manure (Table 2).

Table 1. Biomass production and yield of grain legumes and green manure crops.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Biomass removed for fodder (t ha ⁻¹)	Biomass incorporated (t ha ⁻¹)	N contribution (kg ha ⁻¹)
Sole GG	0.4	7.4	–	–
Sole RG	0.7	6.8	3.1	16.7
Sole SA	–	22.7	12.0	73.5
Sole SR	–	24.9	15.6	82.2
GG + SA	0.3	12.2	4.8	33.5
GG + SR	0.3	13.4	5.5	42.5
RG + SA	0.4	10.3	70.4	50.9
RG + SR	0.3	11.2	7.5	55.8
CD (P = 0.05)	–	1.32	0.11	0.70

^aGG = green gram, RG = red gram, SA = *Sesbania aculeata*, SR = *S. rostrata*.

Table 2. Grain yield of rice (t ha⁻¹).

Treatment ^a	N ₀	N ₅₀	N ₁₀₀	Mean
Sole GG	2.7	3.8	4.6	3.7
Sole RG	3.0	4.3	5.0	4.1
Sole SA	3.6	5.6	6.0	5.0
Sole SR	3.6	5.6	6.1	5.1
GG + SA	3.2	4.8	5.2	4.4
GG + SR	3.3	4.8	5.3	4.5
RG + SA	3.4	5.0	5.4	4.6
RG + SR	3.5	5.1	5.7	4.8
Mean	3.3	4.9	5.4	
		SEd	CD (P = 0.05)	
T		0.17	0.36	
N		0.10	0.21	
T at N		0.29	0.61	
N at T		0.30	0.61	

^aGG = green gram, RG = red gram, SA = *Sesbania aculeata*, SR = *S. rostrata*, SEd = Standard error of the difference.

Comparative growth performance of rice and the weed *Echinochloa oryzicola* in lowland and upland conditions

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Most upland rice cultivars grow successfully in flooded conditions, whereas most lowland rice cultivars can survive in well-watered aerobic soils. It is known that rice has C₃ photosynthesis, whereas the weed *Echinochloa oryzicola* possesses a C₄ photosynthetic pathway. It was hypothesized that plant species with a C₄ photosynthetic pathway had a greater growth rate than C₃ plants (Black 1971). Scientists such as Baskin and Baskin (1978) reviewed several studies and obtained results that generally disagreed with the hypothesis. They

suggested that many factors other than the C₄ pathway are more important in determining plant growth rate. Little is known about the comparative growth performance of rice in upland and lowland field conditions with *E. oryzicola* as a “vegetative mimic” of rice. This study compared the growth performance of rice and *E. oryzicola* under upland and lowland conditions and determined related photosynthetic traits such as stomatal conductance and net photosynthetic rate.

A field experiment was conducted at the Kyoto University

crop science experimental site. Two rice cultivars of different ecotypes—IET1444, an indica upland rice that originated from India, and Nipponbare, a lowland japonica from Japan—and the weed *E. oryzicola* were used in this study. Upland and lowland fields were prepared and laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Fourteen-day-old seedlings were transplanted in the field. In the upland field, watering was done three times a week; in the lowland field, continuous irrigation was employed by maintaining a 2–3-

cm water depth. Five plants from each replication were sampled at 15 and 30 d after transplanting (DAT) for growth analysis. Plant height was measured as length from the soil surface to the longest leaf tip. Leaf area measurements were made with a leaf area meter. Plant parts were categorized into leaf, stem, and root; oven-dried at 65 °C for 96 h; and then weighed.

Calculations of relative growth rate (RGR), leaf area ratio (LAR, ratio of leaf area to total plant weight), and unit leaf rate [ULR (E) = $dW/dT \times 1/LA$, where W = total dry weight, T = time, LA = leaf area, and dW/dT is the value at a time when LA is known] were made using standard equations described by Evans (1972) and Nobel (1983). Photosynthetic responses such as stomatal conductance (g_s) and net photosynthesis (P_n) were also measured using the leaf chamber analysis (LCA-3) machine at 15 and 30 DAT. Student's t tests were used to determine significant differences in growth and photosynthetic responses.

Results showed that *E. oryzicola* had a significantly higher RGR than rice cultivars IET1444 and Nipponbare under both upland and lowland conditions (Table 1). IET1444 had a significantly higher RGR than Nipponbare in the upland, but they had a similar RGR in the lowland (Table 1). The RGR of all test materials declined during the course of the experiment. This was attributed to the decline in ULR because of self-shading (Table 1). There were no consistent differences in ULR between the weed and the two rice cultivars in either upland or lowland conditions (Table 1). The LAR of *E. oryzicola* in both lowland and

upland conditions was considerably higher than that of the two rice cultivars; IET1444 had a significantly higher LAR than Nipponbare during the 30-d growing period. The increase in LAR in all three test materials was observed under lowland conditions from 15 to 30 DAT. In contrast, LAR decreased in the upland field (Table 1). *E. oryzicola*

also had a higher photosynthetic rate than the two rice cultivars (Table 2).

Results show that the weed *E. oryzicola* had a higher and faster growth rate than rice under both upland and lowland conditions; greater differences were observed in the lowland. The overall higher growth performance of *E. oryzicola* was associated with its

Table 1. Relative growth rate (RGR, wk^{-1}), unit leaf rate (ULR, $g\ m^{-2}\ wk^{-1}$), and leaf area ratio (LAR, $cm^2\ g^{-1}$) of two rice cultivars and the weed *E. oryzicola* at 15 and 30 DAT grown under upland and lowland field conditions. (Mean total dry weights per plant are computed based on a \log_{10} scale.)

Growth trait	Sampling date	Weed <i>E. oryzicola</i> ^a	Rice cultivar	
			IET1444	Nipponbare
<i>Lowland field</i>				
RGR	15	0.397 ± 0.0016 a	0.358 ± 0.013 b	0.347 ± 0.007 b
	30	0.320 ± 0.033 a	0.235 ± 0.024 b	0.180 ± 0.021 b
ULR	15	4.393 ± 0.106 a	3.846 ± 0.235 b	1.588 ± 0.621 a
	30	3.813 ± 0.178 ab	3.314 ± 0.358 b	3.848 ± 0.208 b
LAR	15	80.16 ± 1.83 a	78.70 ± 1.99 a	57.70 ± 0.36 b
	30	93.62 ± 2.17 a	73.19 ± 1.79 b	64.35 ± 3.97 c
<i>Upland field</i>				
RGR	15	0.328 ± 0.019 a	0.292 ± 0.022 b	0.180 ± 0.005 c
	30	0.286 ± 0.014 a	0.237 ± 0.025 b	0.119 ± 0.043 c
ULR	15	4.453 ± 0.279 a	4.425 ± 0.274 a	4.387 ± 0.265 a
	30	2.953 ± 0.203 c	3.962 ± 0.291 b	2.727 ± 0.151 c
LAR	15	83.13 ± 4.48 a	74.44 ± 1.44 b	60.23 ± 0.83 c
	30	77.44 ± 1.50 a	67.90 ± 2.93 b	59.89 ± 0.58 c

^aValues for the same entry in a row in the two growing conditions (upland and lowland) followed by the same letter are not significantly different. Shown ± SD.

Table 2. Stomatal conductance (g_s , $cm\ s^{-1}$) and net photosynthesis (P_n , $\mu mol\ CO_2\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}$) of two rice cultivars and the weed *E. oryzicola* at 15 and 30 DAT under upland and lowland field conditions.

Physiological trait	Sampling date	Weed <i>E. oryzicola</i>	Rice cultivar	
			IET1444	Nipponbare
<i>Lowland field</i>				
g_s	15	0.38 b	0.96 a	0.99 a
	30	0.39 c	0.55 b	0.86 a
P_n	15	19.47 a	15.83 b	14.90 b
	30	20.03 a	8.47 c	13.17 b
<i>Upland field</i>				
g_s^a	15	0.37 c	0.81 a	0.75 b
	30	0.22 c	0.33 b	0.72 a
P_n^a	15	13.10 a	12.93 b	13.90 a
	30	14.53 a	9.07 b	5.97 c

^aValues in a row followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$.

higher photosynthetic rate. Between the two rice cultivars, IET1444 had better growth in the upland than Nipponbare; however, it was not associated with photosynthetic response.

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Evaluation of stand establishment techniques in lowland irrigated rice

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Transplanting of rice seedlings is an age-old practice. In recent years, the migration of labor to the industrial sector, especially in India, has led to the nonavailability of labor for transplanting at the appropriate time, resulting in a yield reduction. This method of stand establishment is also laborious and time-consuming and results in drudgery among women workers. Cultivation practices, such as nursery preparation and management, fertilizer and pesticide application and irrigation to the nursery, pulling out seedlings, and transplanting in the main field, account for the major share of cultivation costs. Hence, an alternative method had to be found to overcome problems encountered in using the transplanting technique.

Direct seeding and throwing of seedlings under puddled conditions are viable alternatives to transplanting. Matsushima (1980) cited the advantages of throwing seedlings over a puddled field instead of transplanting. Hence, a study was conducted to evaluate the feasibility of different stand establishment techniques in lowland irrigated rice during the 1999 wet season

(Aug-Dec) and 2000 dry season (Feb-May).

Four stand establishment techniques—transplanting (T_1), seedling throwing (T_2), direct seeding by manual broadcasting (T_3), and wet seeding by a drum seeder (T_4)—were tested in a randomized block design with five replications. The test variety was ADT43 (110 d) and the recommended dose of NPK (125:50:50 kg ha⁻¹) was applied. In transplanting, the recommended 15 × 10-cm spacing was adopted. Seedling throwing consisted of separating two or three seedlings, as is done during normal transplanting, and randomly throwing them in a standing position on a puddled and leveled field to maintain the same plant density per unit area. Twenty-day-old seedlings were used for transplanting and seedling throwing. Seeding rates of 80 and 100 kg ha⁻¹ were used for drum seeding and manual broadcasting, respectively. Sprouted seeds were used for direct seeding. The eight-row drum seeder used in this trial was developed by TNAU's Department of Agricultural Engineering.

The various stand establishment techniques—direct (wet)

seeding by manual broadcasting or a drum seeder or transplanting—showed no significant difference in grain yield in both seasons (see table). In a pooled analysis of two seasons, grain yield was highest in wet seeding by manual broadcasting, closely followed by direct seeding using a drum seeder and traditional transplanting. A similar trend was observed in straw yield. Although wet seeding by manual broadcasting and drum seeding had no significant difference in grain yield, intercultural operations, such as weeding and spraying, could be easily adopted in wet seeding by a drum seeder since there is a definite row arrangement. In both wet-seeding practices and seedling throwing, the cultivation cost was less than with transplanting; less labor cost translated into an increase in income. In both seasons, the net income and benefit-cost ratio were highest in wet seeding by manual broadcasting, closely followed by wet seeding by a drum seeder. Using wet seeding by manual broadcasting and a drum seeder could result in a higher net income and benefit-cost ratio than traditional transplanting. Both direct-seeding